

Full length article

Effect of interface on magnetic exchange coupling in Co/Ru/Co trilayer: From *ab initio* simulations to micromagnetics[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Interfaces play a substantial role for the functional properties of structured magnetic materials and magnetic multilayers. Modeling the functional behavior of magnetic materials requires the treatment of the relevant phenomena at the device level. Properties predicted from the electronic structure and spin dynamics at the atomistic level have to be properly transferred into a continuum level treatment. In this work we show how Co/Ru/Co three layers can be simulated with the continuum theory of micromagnetism, with interface coupling energies and bulk intrinsic properties properly derived from the results of *ab initio* and spin dynamics simulations at different temperatures.

1. Introduction

In magnetic materials, spins/magnetic moments are coupled. This coupling is described by a quantum mechanical effect called exchange. It is the main physical effect/reason for the occurrence of various magnetic configurations with broken symmetry, such as the ferromagnetic, antiferromagnetic, and ferrimagnetic phases, etc. The exchange energy is the energy that misaligned spins/magnetic moments/electrons have to pay and reason that in equilibrium more aligned ones are energetically favored. How strong spins/magnetic moments are coupled is determined by the exchange integral J_{ij} , depending on the overlap of the wave functions of two unpaired electrons or the more classical exchange constant A , which is the prefactor for the following exchange energy density $e_{\text{ex}} = A|\nabla\mathbf{m}|^2$, where \mathbf{m} denotes the magnetization direction [2]. Magnetic phenomena are studied through their dynamic behavior, and the systems are, usually, too large to be investigated at the atomistic level. Thus, the magnetic properties are predicted within the micromagnetic description. In the framework of micromagnetism, all relevant energies are expressed in terms of the unit magnetization vector, which is a continuous function of space and time $\mathbf{m}(t, \mathbf{x})$ [3]. The micromagnetic approach is based on the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert (LLG) equation for $\mathbf{m}(t, \mathbf{x})$, and its solutions require knowledge of appropriate structural and micromagnetic properties. One

approach is to determine these parameters from the intrinsic magnetic properties at the atomic level by mapping the results of the electronic structure calculations to a Heisenberg model. A shortcoming of this method is that the intrinsic magnetic properties are derived for ideal bulk systems, while the real materials are never perfect. Another aspect is that classical micromagnetism does not treat thermal fluctuations explicitly. The intrinsic magnetic properties are assumed to depend on the temperature. The magnetic moment per unit volume is replaced by its average temperature-dependent value which results in the temperature dependent spontaneous magnetization $M_s(T)$. Similarly, the magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant $K(T)$ and the exchange constant $A(T)$ are temperature dependent. They are normally measured at temperature T , at which the specimen is observed.

Within presented work, we aim for interfacial temperature dependencies far below Curie temperature. At the atomistic spin dynamics part of this work an additional stochastic term is added and multiple relaxed domain wall profiles are computed but not at the micromagnetic part. One could improve employed models for higher temperatures using Landau-Lifshitz-Bloch (LLB) equation instead, allowing changes in magnetization length, and more accurately describing the observed enhanced damping and longitudinal relaxation dynamics as shown by [4,5]. This work mainly focuses on the acquisition of intrinsic material properties at interfaces and the path towards it.

[☆] The author's original manuscript (AOM) has been uploaded to the preprint ArXive [1].

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Fig. 1. Simulation of magnetic moment configurations for domain walls across a Ru layer in hcp Co. Top: Schematics of the Co/Ru/Co trilayer. Center: Expected magnetization profile of a domain wall for anti-ferromagnetic coupling across the Ru layer. Bottom: Expected magnetization profile for ferromagnetic coupling across the Ru layer.

In this work, we show how these temperature-dependent parameters can be derived for a system with interfaces from *ab initio* simulations and atomistic spin dynamics (ASD). The interfaces in magnetic structured materials are responsible for the occurrence of many physical phenomena of relevance to modern technological applications [6]. There are a variety of interesting effects that take place in trilayers or multilayers of ferromagnetic materials separated by thin layers of nonmagnetic metals. An observation directly related to the exchange coupling between the ferromagnetic layers is the oscillation of the exchange coupling between layers with the thickness of the non-magnetic layer [7–9]. As an example, we study the coupling of two Co layers in a Co/Ru/Co trilayer. Depending on the thickness of the Ru layer, this coupling is ferromagnetic or antiferromagnetic [10,11]. For the micromagnetic simulations of the trilayer, we assume an interlayer exchange constant between two Co layers $J_{\text{Co,Co}}(T)$, which is temperature dependent. Its value is derived by matching the interface spin configuration obtained from spin dynamic simulations and micromagnetic theory.

The main subject of our study is the spin configuration of a domain wall at the Co|Ru interface. The dynamical behavior of the domain wall structure is simulated as a function of temperature using both ASD simulations and micromagnetic simulations. Fig. 1 shows the expected magnetization distribution across the Ru layer in hexagonal close-packed (hcp) Co.

This paper is structured as follows:

First, we present the general methodology 2. We summarize the procedure 2.1 applied to obtain the intrinsic material properties for micromagnetic simulations of Co/Ru/Co trilayers. We show how we derived the energy of exchange interaction per atom J_{int} across the Ru layer 2.2 using *ab initio* simulations. This is an input parameter for the ASD simulations 2.3 in detail. From the results of the ASD simulations, we derived the input parameters of the micromagnetic simulations 2.4.

Second, we present the results 3. We show the temperature-dependent domain wall profiles in Co/Ru/Co trilayers computed with the ASD simulations for varying Ru thickness 3.1. We derive the temperature dependent intrinsic magnetic properties for micromagnetic simulations from the spin dynamics results 3.2. We use the temperature dependent intrinsic magnetic properties in

micromagnetic simulations of the domain wall profiles for different Ru thickness 3.3. Finally, we draw conclusions 4.

An Author's Original Manuscript (preprint) of this work was previously posted to arXiv [1].

2. Methodology

2.1. Overview

For the micromagnetic simulations of the domain wall profiles of Co/Ru/Co trilayers as a function of temperature, we need the temperature dependent exchange constant $A(T)$ of Co, the temperature dependent anisotropy constant $K(T)$ of Co, and the interlayer exchange constant $J_{\text{Co,Co}}(T)$ between the two Co layers across the Ru interface. The latter will depend on the Ru thickness. In order to derive these parameters we apply the following procedure.

(1) *Ab initio* simulations

Ab initio electronic structure calculations can predict the $T = 0$ K intrinsic magnetic properties such as the total magnetic moment of the system and magnetic (both spin and orbital) moments of individual atoms, the exchange interaction between magnetic moments at various atomic sites, and the magneto-crystalline anisotropy energy. In this work we calculate the exchange energy between atom pairs across the Ru interface J_{int} . For the exchange interaction energy between pairs of magnetic moments J_{ij} in bulk Co we use the values previously computed by Turek et al. [12], and the anisotropy per atom k_u is taken from Moreno et al. [13].

(2) Atomistic spin dynamic simulations

ASD simulations use the exchange energies J_{ij} and J_{int} , and the anisotropy energy k_u per atom as input. These simulations solve the LLG equation for classical spins at the fixed atom sites. Temperature is included through a thermal fluctuation field whose strength is derived from the fluctuation–dissipation theorem. We show that the temperature dependent anisotropy constant $K(T)/K_0$ scales like $(M_s(T)/M_s(0))^3$. Using computed domain wall profiles for bulk Co, we obtain the temperature dependent $A(T)$ and show that $A(T)/A(0)$ scales like $(M_s(T)/M_s(0))^2$. Spin dynamic simulations of magnetization profiles of Co/Ru/Co trilayers show a jump in the average magnetic moment across the Ru layer. We define the angle φ_{int} between the average of magnetic moments of Co touching the left side of the Ru layer and the average of the magnetic moments of the Co atoms touching the right side of the Ru layer.

(3) Micromagnetism

In classical micromagnetism, the magnetic state is described by the vector field $\mathbf{m}(t, \mathbf{x})$. Since we treat the exchange coupling of ferromagnetic layers across interfaces, the magnetization $\mathbf{m}(t, \mathbf{x})$ is not continuous across the interface [14]. We use micromagnetic theory to derive the temperature dependent exchange coupling $J_{\text{Co,Co}}(T)$ across the Ru layer and magnetization profiles in Co/Ru/Co layers from $K(T)$, $A(T)$, and φ_{int} obtained from the ASD simulations.

(4) Validation

We compare the temperature dependent magnetization profiles in Co/Ru/Co layers computed with spin dynamics simulations and micromagnetic simulations.

(5) *Nota Bene*

Here we should mention that, in this work, we mainly focus on the exchange between ferromagnetic layers and how it is affected by the Ru spacer. At this stage we do not take into account the changes in the spin magnetic moment of Co atoms at the Co|Ru interface, as well as the variation of the magneto-crystalline anisotropy of the Co/Ru/Co systems with the width of the Ru spacer. We also do not consider the change of the

Fig. 2. Parameter passing between *ab initio* calculations, spin dynamics simulations and micromagnetic calculations, see 2.1 for more details.

magneto-crystalline anisotropy due to structural phase transition at elevated temperatures.

Furthermore, our study simplifies the interface by considering symmetric exchange only while not accounting for the anti-symmetric Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction, which, as demonstrated by [15], emerges from spin-orbit coupling and broken inversion symmetry at the interface and is known to favor specific chiral domain wall configurations.

In the present model, we focus on the equilibrium exchange coupling between two cobalt layers, more with the aim of bridging length scales through coarse-graining and multiscale simulation than demonstrating the exact magnetization dynamics at Co/Ru/Co stacks. Although domain wall dynamics are not explicitly considered, it is important to acknowledge that interface-induced magnetic moments in the spacer layer may influence magnetic interactions. In our simulations, the change in magnetic moments of Co at the interface is not considered in the atomistic spin dynamics, but the effect of different spin moments of Co at the interface, as well as the induced small magnetic moment in Ru is fully taken into account in the effective coupling across the Ru spacer layer. *Ab-initio* calculations have shown that an orbital magnetic moment can be induced in ruthenium adjacent to cobalt layers due to spin-orbit coupling and broken inversion symmetry [15]. Experimental studies indicate that alloying nonmagnetic spacer layers with Ru does not significantly alter the interlayer exchange coupling for thin spacers. [11]. Additionally, those investigations demonstrate that increasing the magnetic polarization of the spacer layer through Fe or Co doping – up to 10% – results in only minor changes in the coupling energy between the cobalt layers.

The above scheme for parameter passing from the *ab initio* calculations to the ASD, and micromagnetic simulations is schematically shown in Fig. 2.

2.2. *Ab initio* calculations

Electronic structure calculations of Co/Ru/Co systems were done with the Vienna *Ab initio* Simulation Package (VASP) software (version 6.2.1). VASP is a plane-wave basis set implementation [16,17] of the Density Functional Theory within the Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) approximation. [18] Calculations were performed using the generalized gradient approximation of Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) [19] to the exchange–correlation part of the energy functional. We used PAW PBE potentials version 5.4 with 15 and 14 valence electrons for Co and Ru, respectively. The size of the plane-wave basis set was determined by an energy cut-off of 440 eV. The reciprocal space was sampled with a uniform mesh of k points [20] with a separation between the k points of 0.1 \AA^{-1} . For total energy summation, we used the Methfessel-Paxton method [21], with a smearing width of 0.025 eV. Electronic convergence was set to 10^{-7} eV, and geometry optimization was carried out until the norms of all Hellman-Feynman forces [22] were less than 10^{-3} eV/\AA . Equilibrium structure parameters were obtained by performing a set of geometric optimizations (ion positions

and cell shape) at volumes within a 5% range about equilibrium and fitting the energy vs volume data, $E = E(V)$, to the Rose-Vinet equation of state. [23] Co(d_{Co})/Ru(d_{Ru})/ Co(d_{Co}) multilayers were modeled as periodic supercells of the hcp unit cell, with the c -axis oriented along the x -direction. A supercell comprises two Co layers, with layer width $0.8 \text{ nm} \leq d_{\text{Co}} \leq 2.6 \text{ nm}$ (from 4 to 13 Co atomic layers) each, separated by a few Ru atomic layers (1, 2, and 3) as shown in Fig. 3.

From the calculated total energies, we can now calculate an effective exchange interaction energy per atom as following:

$$E_{\text{int}} = (E_{\text{FM}} - E_{\text{AFM}})/2 \quad (1)$$

where $E_{\text{AFM/FM}}$ are the total energies of the AFM/FM configurations. E_{int} represents the exchange interaction of the left bulk with the right bulk across the Ru interface.

According to the Heisenberg model, we will add E_{int} to the total energy when the spins across interface are oriented in parallel, and subtract E_{int} if the spins are oriented anti-parallel. Thus, E_{int} can be calculated by subtracting the total energies E_{FM} and E_{AFM} . With N_{int} Co atoms in the layer adjacent to the interface, the effective Co-Co exchange coupling per pair across the Ru spacer is, simply, given by:

$$J_{\text{int}} = E_{\text{int}}/N_{\text{int}} \quad (2)$$

The resulting coupling energies for 1, 2 and 3 monolayers of Ru as a function of the width of Co layers are shown in Fig. 4. For the ASD calculations we have chosen the following values for the effective coupling between Co pairs separated by a Ru spacer: $J_{\text{int},1} = -1.376 \text{ mRy}$ ($-3 \times 10^{-21} \text{ J}$), $J_{\text{int},2} = -0.7301 \text{ mRy}$ ($-1.59 \times 10^{-21} \text{ J}$), and $J_{\text{int},3} = 0.3011 \text{ mRy}$ ($0.656 \times 10^{-21} \text{ J}$) for a Ru spacer of 1, 2, and 3 atomic layers, respectively.

Following the work of Moreno et al. [13], we compute the zero temperature exchange constant of bulk hcp Co parallel to the c -axis using

$$A(0) = \frac{1}{4V_{\text{at}}} \sum_i J_{0i} \cdot (r_i - r_0)^2 \quad (3)$$

where i iterates over all neighboring atoms of 0-th atom, J_{0i} is the exchange interaction energy, r_i is the atom positions along the c -axis, and $V_{\text{at}} = 1.1 \times 10^{-29} \text{ m}^3$ is the volume per atom. This gives $A(0) = 52.78 \text{ pJ/m}$. Which is close to some reported values though they vary from 30.2 pJ/m [24] to 47.3 pJ/m [12]. Note within this study, in the next steps we do not evaluate the full tensorial form of the exchange stiffness. Instead, we focus on the direction perpendicular to the interface, in order to derive the effective coupling constant across the Ru layer. The investigation of the anisotropic exchange integrals in the bulk Co and how it might change with the Ru interlayer would require more extensive investigation.

2.3. Spin dynamic simulations

We use the classical spin dynamics method to bridge the gap between density functional theory, which calculates supercells of up to hundreds of atoms, and micromagnetics, which simulates systems on the micrometer scale containing billions of atoms, albeit on the continuum level. Our ASD usage lies somewhere in the middle, simulating

Fig. 3. Sketch of a Co/Ru/Co slab. Both Co bulk parts are configured in two different states (i) into a ferromagnetic (FM) state and (ii) into an anti-ferromagnetic (AFM) state. The calculated total energies $E_{AFM/FM}$ of the AFM/FM configurations can be factorized in the contributions from the two bulk-like Co slabs E_{Co} , and exchange interaction energy at the interface E_{int} .

Fig. 4. Effective Heisenberg interactions J_{int} between Co atoms separated by a Ru spacer as a function of the width of Co layers d_{Co} and Ru spacer d_{Ru} .

around 1 million atoms. This is necessary to capture the collective phenomena that arise due to finite temperature and determine the temperature dependence of the magnetic properties of the material, such as saturation magnetization $M_s(T)$, magnetocrystalline anisotropy $K(T)$, exchange stiffness $A(T)$ and, in turn, the domain wall width $\delta_{DW}(T)$.

The simulated system is described by the following Hamiltonian:

$$\mathcal{H} = - \sum_{ij} J_{ij} \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j - \sum_i k_u (\vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{e}_k)^2 - \sum_i \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{B}_{ext} \quad (4)$$

where J_{ij} are the exchange interaction energies between pairs of magnetic moments i and j , k_u is the magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy, \vec{e}_k is the easy-axis direction ($\vec{e}_k = (0, 0, 1)$ throughout this work), \vec{S}_i is the normalized moment vector at i th site ($|\vec{S}_i| = 1$), and \vec{B}_{ext} is the external magnetic field vector. Note that each pair is counted twice (J_{ij} is halved to account for double counting).

The exchange interaction energies J_{ij} are taken from ab initio calculations by Turek et al. [12]. 38 nearest unique exchange interaction pairs were taken into account, corresponding to a distance cutoff of about 1 nm. For the anisotropy energy per atom we used the value $k_u = 5.83 \cdot 10^{-24}$ J/atom [13], corresponding to a macroscopic magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant of $K(0) = 0.547$ MJ/m³. These values yield a $T = 0$ K domain wall width of $\delta_{DW} = \pi \sqrt{A/K} = 31.35$ nm.

In this work, we simplify the actual Co/Ru/Co interface by replacing the influence of the Ru atoms with an effective exchange interaction J_{int} (Section 2.2). Apart from this effective exchange interaction, there are no other interactions between atoms of the two bulks. Thus we write for the Hamiltonian for the Co/Ru/Co trilayer:

$$\sum_{ij} J_{ij} \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j = \sum_{i,j \in C_{BL}} J(\vec{r}_{ij}) \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j +$$

$$\sum_{i,j \in C_{BR}} J(\vec{r}_{ij}) \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j + \sum_{i \in C_{IL}, j \in C_{IR}} J_{int} \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \delta(\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j - \vec{r}_{int}) + \sum_{i \in C_{BL}, j \in C_{BR}} (-1) \cdot J(\vec{r}_{ij} - \vec{l}_z) \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \quad (5)$$

where C_{BL} , C_{BR} are sets containing spins in the left and right bulk, respectively, C_{IL} and C_{IR} are sets of spins on the left and right side of the interface and J_{int} is the specific energy of exchange interaction across the interface calculated from bilinear coupling in Section 2.2. \vec{r}_{int} is the relative position of the nearest neighbors across the interface and \vec{l}_z is the size of the simulation domain in the z -direction. Note that $C_{IL} \subset C_{BL}$, $C_{IR} \subset C_{BR}$ and $C_{BL} \cup C_{BR}$ contains all spins.

The first two terms describe the exchange interactions inside the left and right Co bulk. The third term stands for the interaction across the Ru interface. The fourth term stands for the antiperiodic boundary condition in the z -direction, which helps to pin the domain wall in the middle of the simulation domain. Periodic boundary conditions in the (x,y) -direction are also employed in this model, but not explicitly mentioned in the Hamiltonian above.

The atomistic ASD approach is based on the LLG equation for individual spins:

$$\frac{d\vec{S}_i}{dt} = - \frac{\gamma}{1 + \alpha^2} \vec{S}_i \times \vec{H}_i^{eff} - \frac{\gamma\alpha}{1 + \alpha^2} \vec{S}_i \times (\vec{S}_i \times \vec{H}_i^{eff}) \quad (6)$$

where γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, α is the Gilbert damping parameter and \vec{H}_i^{eff} is the effective field experienced by i th spin. To introduce temperature T , a stochastic Gaussian field $\vec{b}_i(t)$ with variance of $\sqrt{\frac{2\alpha k_B T}{\Delta t \gamma \mu_B}}$ is added to the effective field:

$$\vec{H}_i^{eff} = - \frac{d\mathcal{H}}{d\vec{S}_i} + \vec{b}_i(t) \quad (7)$$

where Δt is the simulation timestep. An ASD simulation is then formally just an integration of the LLG equation. In this work, Heun's method is used for numerical integration with a timestep Δt small enough to keep the integration error negligible. The damping rate was chosen as $\alpha = 0.05$ based on the speed of convergence. The choice of damping parameter does not influence the domain wall width, since it is measured in the equilibrated state.

The cross section of the simulation domain is chosen to be large enough such that the thermal noise does not destroy the domain wall. The length is chosen such that the entire domain wall profile is simulated. In this work, the simulation domain consists of $50 \times 50 \times 240$ unit cells for hcp Co. Each unit cell contains 2 Co atoms at fractional coordinates $(0, 0, 0)$ and $(1/3, 1/3, 1/2)$, and the lattice parameters are $a = 2.47$ Å and $c/a = \sqrt{8/3}$. The simulation domain for the Co/Ru/Co systems is constructed by altering the original hcp Co simulation domain: first, a simulation domain of $50 \times 50 \times 240$ hcp Co unit cells is created, then n central layers of atoms are removed to account for the Ru interface, and then the pairwise exchange interactions at the interface are modified.

Fig. 5. Magnetization configuration at a ferromagnetic interface.

All ASD calculations were carried out by our unpublished and in-house developed software. The main result of the ASD stage in this work is the magnetization profile along the z -direction $M(z) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, which is calculated as the average of all spins in the individual hcp layers.

2.4. Micromagnetism

Micromagnetism [25] is a continuum theory. The energy functional is expressed in terms of the unit magnetization vector $\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x})$, which is a continuous function of position \mathbf{x} . We now derive the micromagnetic energy of the domain configurations shown in Fig. 1. We assume translational symmetry in the xy plane. In our approach we neglect magnetostatic interactions. There is no energy difference between a Bloch or a Néel wall [26]. We restrict the vector \mathbf{m} to lie in the xz plane and describe its direction with the angle φ from the positive z axis. We start with the energy of the domain wall in bulk Co:

$$E(\varphi) = \int_a^b \left(A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \right)^2 + K \sin^2 \varphi \right) dz \quad (8)$$

For a simple domain wall $\varphi(a) = \pi$ and $\varphi(b) = 0$. In order to express the energy of a domain wall across a Co/Ru/Co trilayer, we split the energy (8) into two parts and add a surface energy term:

$$E_{wi}(\varphi) = \int_a^0 \left(A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \right)^2 + K \sin^2 \varphi \right) dz + \int_0^b \left(A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \right)^2 + K \sin^2 \varphi \right) dz - J_{Co,Co} (\mathbf{m}_{left} \cdot \mathbf{m}_{right}) \quad (9)$$

The last term considers the coupling across the Ru layer. It is the interface energy expressed in terms of the magnetization vectors \mathbf{m}_{left} and \mathbf{m}_{right} left and right of the interface, respectively. We can write the interface energy in terms of the interface angle

$$E_{int} = -J_{Co,Co} \cos(\varphi_{int}) \quad (10)$$

with

$$\varphi_{int} = \varphi_{left} - \varphi_{right} \quad (11)$$

From the magnetization configuration in Fig. 5 we see that we can use symmetry to express φ_{right} in terms of φ_{left}

$$\varphi_{right} = \pi - \varphi_{left} \quad (12)$$

The interface energy is

$$E_{int} = -J_{Co,Co} \cos(2\varphi_{left} - \pi). \quad (13)$$

or

$$E_{int} = J_{Co,Co} \cos(2\varphi_{left}). \quad (14)$$

Owing to symmetry that the twist of the magnetization in the left and the right part consumes the same amount of energy. Therefore, we can write for the total energy (see also Fig. 5) as:

$$E_{wi}(\varphi) = 2 \int_a^0 \left(A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \right)^2 + K \sin^2 \varphi \right) dz + J_{Co,Co} \cos(2\varphi(0)) \quad (15)$$

For the functional

$$E(\varphi) = \int_a^0 \left(e \left(\varphi(z), \frac{d\varphi(z)}{dz} \right) \right) + E_{int}(\varphi(0)) \quad (16)$$

the Euler Lagrange equation is

$$\frac{\partial e}{\partial \varphi} - \frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{\partial e}{\partial \frac{d\varphi}{dz}} \right) = 0 \quad (17)$$

The surface energy E_{int} at $z = 0$ leads the following boundary condition

$$\frac{dE_{int}}{d\varphi} + \frac{\partial e}{\partial \frac{d\varphi}{dz}} = 0. \quad (18)$$

The Euler Lagrange equations in micromagnetics and the boundary conditions arising from surface energies are discussed in [27] (see equations I.44 to I.47 in [27]). For our problem we can write the following relations.

$$e = 2A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \right)^2 + 2K \sin^2 \varphi \quad (19)$$

$$E_{int} = J_{Co,Co} \cos(2\varphi(0)) \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial e}{\partial \varphi} = 4K \sin \varphi \cos \varphi \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\partial e}{\partial \frac{d\varphi}{dz}} = 4A \frac{d\varphi}{dz} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{dE_{int}}{d\varphi} = -2J_{Co,Co} \sin(2\varphi(0)) \quad (23)$$

With the above equations we rewrite (17)

$$4K \sin \varphi \cos \varphi = 4A \frac{d^2 \varphi}{dz^2} \quad (24)$$

$$2K \sin \varphi \cos \varphi = 2A \frac{d^2 \varphi}{dz^2} \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{d}{d\varphi} (K \sin^2 \varphi) = 2A \frac{d^2 \varphi}{dz^2} \quad (26)$$

We multiply (26) with $d\varphi/dz$ and integrate (see [27] equation I.38)

$$K \sin^2 \varphi(0) - K \sin^2 \varphi(z) = A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \Big|_0 \right)^2 - A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \Big|_z \right)^2 \quad (27)$$

At $z = -\infty$ the first term on the left hand side and the first term on the right hand side of (27) vanish as we are in the center of the magnet. Following the arguments in [27], we obtain

$$K \sin^2 \varphi(z) = A \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dz} \right)^2 \quad (28)$$

Let us now have a closer look at the boundary condition at $z = 0$. From (18) we obtain with (22) and (23)

$$-2J_{int} \sin(2\varphi(0)) + 4A \frac{d\varphi}{dz} \Big|_0 = 0 \quad (29)$$

From (28) we get

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dz} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{K}{A}} \sin \varphi \quad (30)$$

In our setting $\frac{d\varphi}{dz} < 0$ (see Fig. 5). Therefore we take the right hand side of (30) with the minus sign and insert it into (29). At $z = 0$ we have

$$-2J_{Co,Co} \sin(2\varphi) - 4\sqrt{AK} \sin \varphi = 0 \quad (31)$$

Fig. 6. Illustration of a conventional domain wall and the magnetization distribution of a Co/Ru/Co trilayer with ferromagnetic coupling. The jump in the magnetization Δm_z is used to compute the temperature dependent interface coupling constant for micromagnetics $J_{\text{Co,Co}}$.

With $\sin(2\varphi) = 2 \sin(\varphi) \cos(\varphi)$ we obtain

$$-4J_{\text{Co,Co}} \sin \varphi \cos \varphi - 4\sqrt{AK} \sin \varphi = 0 \quad (32)$$

We now evaluate Eq. (32) at $z = 0$. Using $\varphi_{\text{left}} = \varphi(0)$ we can write for $\varphi_{\text{left}} \neq 0$ we obtain

$$J_{\text{Co,Co}} \cos \varphi_{\text{left}} = -\sqrt{AK} \quad (33)$$

and can express the angle of the magnetization at the interface in terms of the bulk temperature dependent properties $A(T)$ and $K(T)$ and the temperature dependent interface coupling constant $J_{\text{Co,Co}}(T)$

$$\cos \varphi_{\text{left}} = -\frac{\sqrt{AK}}{J_{\text{Co,Co}}} \quad (34)$$

The jump of the z -component of the magnetization across the interface, Δm_z was computed by averaging the spin dynamic results near the interface. Eq. (34) can be expressed with that jump as

$$J_{\text{Co,Co}} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{AK}}{\Delta m_z / 2} \quad (35)$$

In the results Section 3.2, we will use Eq. (35) to obtain the temperature dependent coupling constant $J_{\text{Co,Co}}(T)$ from the interface angle φ_{int} , which was computed by ASD simulations, and the bulk properties $A(T)$ and $K(T)$.

Fig. 6 illustrates the jump of the magnetization across the interface for ferromagnetic coupling of the two Co layers in comparison to a conventional domain wall.

3. Results

3.1. Domain wall profiles from ASD

In the first stage, we use the ASD to calculate temperature-dependent domain wall properties in bulk hcp Co and compare with previously obtained results [13]. The ASD calculation starts with an initial configuration where the left half of the spins is $\vec{S} = (0, 0, -1)$ and the right half is $\vec{S} = (0, 0, 1)$. The simulation then runs for 2,400,000 steps and the initial configuration relaxes into equilibrated domain walls.

The magnetization profile of the averaged configuration should then follow the shape of hyperbolic tangens for the z component of the unit magnetization vector

$$m_z(z) = m_s \tanh(\pi(z - z_0)/\delta_{\text{DW}}) \quad (36)$$

where $m_s = M_s(T)/M_s(0)$ is the reduced temperature dependent magnetization, z_0 is the domain wall center, and δ_{DW} is the domain wall width. The simulated magnetization profile is then fitted into the above equation in order to obtain values for the free parameters m_s , z_0 and δ_{DW} .

The magnetization spin-dynamics profiles, their average profiles over temperature and the results of this fitting are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. In this work, the zero-temperature domain wall width is larger than in [13], but increases more slowly with temperature. Also, the saturation magnetization decreases more slowly with temperature and indicates a Curie temperature of about $T_C \approx 1500$ K, compared to $T_C = 1300$ K in [13]. This is caused by a different input set of exchange interactions.

Calculating domain wall properties in the Co/Ru/Co trilayer with ASD is performed analogically to that in bulk hcp Co. The initial configuration of the system is set according to sign of the interface exchange coupling. In case of 1 and 2 Ru layers, all spins are set to $\vec{S} = (0, 0, 1)$ and the system relaxes into an antiferromagnetic domain wall. In case of 3 Ru layers, spins in the left bulk are set to $\vec{S} = (0, 0, -1)$, spins in the right bulk are set to $\vec{S} = (0, 0, 1)$, and the system relaxes into a conventional domain wall. The calculation is set to run for 800,000 steps. The resulting averaged magnetization profiles are shown in Fig. 9. The left most image shows the magnetization profile for one monolayer of Ru atoms separating the two Co slabs. The exchange coupling across the Ru spacer is antiferromagnetic. For two monolayers Ru the antiferromagnetic coupling strength is reduced by about a factor of two. The corresponding magnetization profile is shown in the center of Fig. 9. For three monolayers of Ru atoms, the coupling is ferromagnetic. The domain wall, which shows a jump of the magnetization at the interface, is given in the right most image.

3.2. Intrinsic properties for micromagnetics

The acquisition of all temperature dependent intrinsic material properties of hcp Co bulk follows the temperature dependence of the saturation magnetization M_s .

The ASD method was used to calculate temperature dependence of magnetocrystalline anisotropy $K(T)$. We initially start with all spins pointing into the $-z$ direction. Then we apply a positive external field and integrate the stochastic LLG equation. The field is chosen such that the magnetization reverses during the simulation time. From sampling the anisotropy energy during magnetization reversal, we obtain $E_{\text{anis}}(M_z)$. For a Stoner-Wohlfarth particle this energy curve is a parabola [28], its maximum corresponds to the anisotropy constant K times the particle volume V . The Stoner-Wohlfarth switching field is $H_{\text{sw}} = 2K/(\mu_0 M_s)$.

The simulation domain consists of $10 \times 10 \times 10$ and the initial configuration is ferromagnetic (all spins $\vec{S} = (0, 0, -1)$). An external magnetic field \vec{H}_{ext} in the $+z$ direction is turned on and the ferromagnetic configuration slowly goes from $M_z = -1$ to $M_z = 1$. For sampling $E_{\text{anis}}(M_z)$ during magnetization reversal we do not need to apply an external field which is sufficiently large to cause switching during the simulation time. Here we set H_{ext} a value slightly larger than an estimate of the Stoner-Wohlfarth switching field. We approximate $M_s(T)$ with the Bloch's law

$$M_s^{\text{est}}(T) = M_s(0) \left(1 - \left(\frac{T}{T_C} \right)^{3/2} \right), \quad (37)$$

where T_C is the Curie temperature. For the temperature dependence of the anisotropy we assume the Callen-Callen law [29]

$$K^{\text{est}}(T) = K(0) \left(\frac{M_s(T)}{M_s(0)} \right)^3 \quad (38)$$

Fig. 7. Magnetization configurations after relaxation steps for different temperatures of hcp Co bulk. Colored regions show the averaged magnetization over one atomic Co layer of around 100 separate spin-dynamics simulations. The dot-dashed lines highlight the average of those profiles for each specific temperature.

Fig. 8. Temperature dependence of domain wall width and saturation magnetization in hcp Co extracted via fit of the Eq. (36). Results from Moreno et al. [13] are shown for comparison.

Fig. 9. Magnetization profiles across the Co/Ru/Co system for various temperatures and Ru spacer thicknesses. Left: Ru spacer thickness is 1 atomic layer, the coupling across the spacer is antiferromagnetic; Center: Ru spacer thickness is 2 atomic layers, the coupling across the spacer is antiferromagnetic; Right: Ru spacer thickness is 3 atomic layers, the coupling across the spacer is ferromagnetic. The dot-dashed lines highlight the average of those profiles for each specific temperature.

Fig. 10. Energy barrier between magnetization state $M_z = +1$ and $M_z = -1$. Achieved through sampling of anisotropy energy plotted against magnetization in the z -direction for various temperatures in bulk hcp Co. Each dot represents an average of 50,000 ASD steps.

Fig. 11. Temperature dependence of calculated anisotropy, saturation magnetization, and its third power in bulk hcp Co. Saturation magnetization (blue dots), spin-dynamics estimated anisotropy constant with energy barriers (black dots), anisotropy constant following Callen-Callens law (red crosses) and a linear fit (dashed line).

We use Eqs. (37) and (38) to approximate the Stoner-Wohlfarth switching field which is used as value for the external field for simulating magnetization reversal. We validated that varying the external magnetic field up to several times H_{sw} has negligible effect on the resulting value of anisotropy $K(T)$ which supports this approach as a valid source of temperature-dependent anisotropy, instead of having to calculate the whole hysteresis curve or employing constrained Monte Carlo techniques [30].

The anisotropy energy value is extracted from sampling the anisotropy energy component during the ASD calculation. This energy is then plotted against magnetization z -component (E_{anis} vs M_z) in Fig. 10. We can clearly see the energy barrier between $M_z = -1$ and $M_z = +1$ which corresponds to $K(T)V$. Furthermore, the data can be accurately fitted using a parabola $E_{anis} = qM_z^2 + k$, illustrating consistency with the Stoner-Wohlfarth model. The anisotropy energy was calculated as difference between highest and lowest energy in Fig. 10: $KV = \max(E_{anis}) - \min(E_{anis})$.

Fig. 12. Intrinsic material properties derived from the ASD simulations. Left: Reduced temperature dependent magnetization $M_s(T)/M_s(0)$. Center: Anisotropy constant $K(T)$. Right: Exchange stiffness constant $A(T)$.

Fig. 13. The interface exchange coupling extracted from the Δm_z relation from the Eq. (35) in units of J/m^2 .

Fig. 11 shows the calculated temperature dependence of $K(T)$. The anisotropy constant decreases linearly with temperature up to about 1600 K where it goes to zero. At low temperatures, it agrees exceptionally well with the Callen-Callen law. Therefore, we use Eq. (38) for $K(T)$ in the micromagnetic simulations.

In order to obtain the exchange constant $A(T)$, we assume a general power law

$$A_\beta(T) = A(0) \left(\frac{M_s(T)}{M_s(0)} \right)^\beta \quad (39)$$

and minimize the squared error in the domain wall width

$$F(\beta) = \sum_i \left(\delta_{DW}(T_i) - \pi \sqrt{\frac{A_\beta(T_i)}{K(T_i)}} \right)^2 \quad (40)$$

In (40) the sum is over all temperature T_i used in the ASD simulations of the domain wall width shown (see Fig. 8). For minimizing (40), we used the adaptive nonlinear least-squares algorithm method (NL2SOL) by Dennis et al. [31] as implemented in the Dakota suite [32]. From nonlinear least-square fit we obtained $\beta = 2$.

Fig. 12 shows the temperature dependent intrinsic material properties for hcp Co.

In addition to the bulk properties of hcp Co, we need the coupling constant $J_{Co,Co}(T)$ across the Ru layer. Given the angle of the magnetic moments between the interfaces φ_{int} and with the knowledge about bulk exchange constant $A(T)$ and magnetocrystalline anisotropy $K(T)$ at specific temperature T we can use Eq. (35) to obtain the temperature coupling constant from the ASD simulations.

Table 1

Input parameters for micromagnetic simulations of Co/Ru/Co trilayers. The columns give the number Ru monolayers n , the temperature T , exchange constant A , the anisotropy constant K and the coupling constant $J_{Co,Co}$.

n	T (K)	A (pJ/m)	K (MJ/m ³)	$J_{Co,Co}$ (J/m ²)
1	1	52.78	0.547	-0.05657
2	1	52.78	0.547	-0.03000
3	1	52.78	0.547	0.01236
1	100	50.29	0.509	-0.053234
2	100	50.29	0.509	-0.02820
3	100	50.29	0.509	0.01182
1	300	45.04	0.431	-0.04749
2	300	45.04	0.431	-0.02535
3	300	45.04	0.431	0.01044
1	500	39.53	0.355	-0.04046
2	500	39.53	0.355	-0.02082
3	500	39.53	0.355	0.00919

We start from the ASD simulation of the magnetization profiles across the Co/Ru/Co trilayer presented in Section 3.1 and compute the average magnetic moments of the Co atoms left and right of the interface. Using the notation of Section 2.3, the average magnetic moments are

$$\mathbf{m}_{left}^{spindyn} = \frac{1}{|C_{IL}|} \sum_{i \in C_{IL}} \vec{S}_i \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{right}^{spindyn} = \frac{1}{|C_{IR}|} \sum_{i \in C_{IR}} \vec{S}_i \quad (42)$$

where $|C_{IL}|$ and $|C_{IR}|$ are the number of Co atoms in the sets of atoms to the left and to the right of the interface, respectively. We now compute the angle φ_{int} between the two unit vectors $\mathbf{m}_{left}^{spindyn}$ and $\mathbf{m}_{right}^{spindyn}$.

Fig. 13 shows the resulting coupling constant $J_{Co,Co}(T)$ for one, two, and three monolayers of Ru atoms between the Co layers as a function of temperature T .

In Table 1 we show selected values for the micromagnetic input parameters.

3.3. Domain wall profiles from micromagnetics

In the final stage of the multiscale simulation process, we compute the magnetization profiles across Co/Ru/Co layers using micromagnetic simulations based on the temperature-dependent parameters derived in Section 2.4. The micromagnetic profiles shown in Fig. 14 were obtained by minimizing the energy functional (Eq. (15)) using a one-dimensional finite element discretization. The total simulation length of 100 nm was divided into 100 finite elements, and the energy was numerically minimized with the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) algorithm as implemented in the Python SciPy library. This approach ensures

Fig. 14. Comparison of temperature dependent magnetization profiles obtained from the ASD and algebraic solution. The colored surfaces show the ensemble of all spin-dynamics simulations. The white dotted lines show the average values (see Fig. 9), the dashed white line demonstrate the results from algebraic solution. Left and Mid: Antiferromagnetic coupling across one and two monolayers Ru. Right: Ferromagnetic coupling across three monolayer Ru atoms. Note: We show only the right side of the profiles because of symmetry.

accurate equilibrium configurations while maintaining computational efficiency.

A direct comparison between micromagnetic and atomistic spin dynamics (ASD) results demonstrates excellent agreement at low and moderate temperatures, confirming the validity of the derived temperature-dependent parameters for continuum modeling. At higher temperatures, slight deviations occur between the micromagnetic profiles and the averaged ASD results. These discrepancies likely originate from two factors: (i) the classical LLG-based micromagnetic model neglects longitudinal fluctuations, which become significant near the Curie temperature, and (ii) the limited number of ASD profiles used for averaging introduces statistical noise. Nevertheless, the overall similarity between the two approaches validates the coarse-graining procedure and the scaling laws for $A(T) \propto (M_s(T))^2$ and $K(T) \propto (M_s(T))^3$.

The use of finite elements in micromagnetic simulations offers a significant advantage over ASD for large-scale problems. While ASD is essential for capturing atomistic effects and deriving accurate temperature-dependent parameters, it becomes computationally prohibitive for device-scale simulations. In contrast, micromagnetic models can efficiently handle systems on the micrometer scale, such as magnetic read heads in data storage technologies, where demagnetized remanent states are often stabilized by Ru interlayers. For such applications, accurate temperature-dependent coupling constants are critical, and our multiscale workflow provides these parameters in a form suitable for continuum modeling.

4. Conclusion

This work demonstrates a systematic multiscale approach to bridge atomistic and continuum descriptions of magnetic multilayers. By passing zero-temperature parameters obtained from ab initio calculations to atomistic spin dynamics simulations, we derive temperature-dependent values for spontaneous magnetization, exchange stiffness, and anisotropy constants. In addition to these bulk properties, we compute the temperature-dependent interface coupling constant for Co/Ru/Co trilayers, enabling accurate micromagnetic modeling of systems with interlayer exchange coupling.

The micromagnetic simulations, based on finite element discretization and BFGS energy minimization, show excellent agreement with ASD results at low and moderate temperatures. Deviations at higher temperatures highlight the limitations of the conventional LLG-based micromagnetic model, which neglects longitudinal fluctuations and interface Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya interaction (DMI). Incorporating these effects through a Landau–Lifshitz–Bloch (LLB) framework and extended interface models would improve accuracy at elevated temperatures.

The advantage of the micromagnetic approach lies in its scalability. While ASD is indispensable for parameter extraction, it is computationally infeasible for simulating device-scale systems, such as magnetic read heads, where Ru interlayers are commonly used to achieve demagnetized remanent states. Our workflow provides the necessary temperature-dependent coupling constants for such large-scale simulations, enabling predictive modeling of magnetic devices under realistic thermal conditions. This capability is essential for designing next-generation magnetic storage technologies and other applications where interface-driven phenomena play a critical role.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sergiu Arapan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jan Priessnitz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Alexander Kovacs:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dominik Legut:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Harald Oezelt:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation. **David Böhm:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Data curation. **Markus Gusenbauer:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Thomas Schrefl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data to reproduce the figures 7, 9, 12, 13 and 14 has been made available at [10.5281/zenodo.15083976](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083976).

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